

Comparative Analysis of Computer-Assisted -Instruction and Reinforcement Strategies on Learning Outcome in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Delta State

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Abstracts

The study investigated the comparative analysis of computer-assisted -instruction and reinforcement strategies on learning outcome in chemistry among secondary school students in Delta state four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the planned variation research design. Two experimental groups were used for this research which comprised of two urban and rural schools respectively. The sample consisted of 512 SSII chemistry students in four public secondary schools in delta state. The chemistry assessment test was the instrument used for data collection which was validated by experts in the field ($r=0.75$). The hypotheses were analyzed using t- test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed there was a significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of students taught with computer assisted- instruction and students exposed to reinforcement learning approach in favour of computer assisted-instruction. In light of the findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that the use of computer-assisted instruction in teaching difficult chemistry concept improves students' learning outcomes more than reinforcement approach. it is therefore, recommended that government and school heads should make provision of computer and education soft wares in secondary schools and train teachers in the methodology and learning of chemistry.

Keywords: computer assisted; chemistry; instruction; learning; reinforcement; students

Introduction

Chemistry has been mentioned among the subjects that are considered significant for the scientific and economic development of countries (fowotade, 2016). The role of chemistry in national development is quite enormous. Chemistry has contributed immensely in the area of health, teaching, agriculture, among others (Ekundayo, 2022). According to Emmanuel, Emanuel and Rose (2021) they opined that through chemistry, Nigeria as well as other developing countries acquired the needed level of development. It is considered a fundamental and central science in different working areas such as medicine, pharmacy, biochemistry, engineering, microbiology, textile industry, agriculture, and petroleum products separation (Bhargava, 2016). It holds a central position in the science world and therefore, requires effective teaching that will boost students understanding of the chemistry concept.

It is sad to note, that the subject chemistry has not gotten the required attention needed for effective learning. Students have continued to perform poorly in external examinations. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) examiners' report of 2005 to 2014 have always reported students' inability in answering questions in some chemistry concepts. These concepts are electrolysis, radioactivity, chemical equilibrium, hybridization, mixture and separation techniques and chemical reaction. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) chief examiner report (WAEC, 2015 & NECO 2015) reported that for some years back, students have avoided, failed and could not tackle adequately the electrolysis and rate of chemical reaction. Agu and Okafor (2021): their study in anambra state revealed a consistent correlation between poor student performance in WAEC and NECO chemistry exams, emphasizing that challenging topics like electrolysis and equilibrium remain poorly understood. They attributed this to ineffective teaching methods and insufficient use of technology in instruction. Premium times (2023): the report analyzed WAEC results and identified chemistry as one of the most challenging subjects for Nigerian students. It cited specific topics such as electrolysis and chemical equilibrium, noting that poor foundational knowledge and a reliance on rote learning were significant obstacles to student success. Chemistry consists of some difficult topics that need active teaching methods and adequate instructional materials to allow students develop understanding and competencies in the subject.

Scholars have reported that a lot of factors are responsible for students' failure in chemistry but it lies mostly on the pedagogy. Students' persistence poor performance has been partly ascribed to inadequate teaching and instructional methods adopted by science teacher (Ameh and Dantani 2012). The federal republic of Nigeria in the national policy on education (FRN 2013) recognized the importance of teachers by stating that no nation's educational system could be greater than the quality of her teachers. This means that the teachers remain the major input in any educational system and their quality of teaching is

undoubtedly one of the most important factors shaping the teaching and learning process as well as the achievement of students (Iyaboyi and Muftau, 2014).

Researchers opined that the pedagogy skill of the teacher is a powerful force (Amusan 2016). It has been observed that teachers' activity mostly dwells on mere recitation of knowledge without involving practical demonstration of learning that will enhance students' ability to acquire skills, have deep retention of knowledge, develop self-reliance syndrome, and create knowledge on their own without much help from the teacher and this style of teaching by teachers will be an impediment to learning and may eventually lead to failure in chemistry. Teachers have frequently adopted the traditional method of teaching which results to little or no learning in the teaching of some difficult concept in chemistry. Menon (2015) posited that the traditional approach of lecture and note taking has lost its effectiveness in this modern day. Ineffective teaching methods and insufficient instructional resources are most problematic for effective and successful chemistry teaching and learning and make it difficult for some learners (Ejidike & Oyelana, 2015). This necessitated the need to adopt an instructional method that is an activity based and have the potential to stimulate and motivate learning. Chemistry subject needs a pedagogical approach that will foster learning through practical demonstration, seeing learning taking place in a natural form. One of the most effective ways to make teaching and learning interesting and effective is taking advantage of instructional technologies, especially the computers (Tareef, 2014).

The computer assisted instruction (CAI) is an interactive instructional strategy where the teacher uses computer to present the instructional materials to the students and monitor the learning process. Computer could be assessed individually or as a group unlike a conventional classroom where students are lumped together irrespective of their individual differences and class size (Laleye, 2019). In the teacher centered method of teaching, teachers are the key source of information and transmitters of knowledge while the students are passive receiving information. This method of teaching needs to be complemented, more especially in the era of ICT, where the role of a teacher has shifted from being the key source of information and transmitter of knowledge to that of becoming a collaborator and a co-learner (Samaila, Makinde and Zambwa 2016). Part of the drive towards greater use of modern technology in education is equipping teachers and learners of today with skills that will help them to think and act globally (Laleye, 2019).

Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) also revealed in their study that CAI engages learners, makes them active participants in class as well as motivate the students. Samuel and Okonkwo (2020) also found out that low academic self-concept in chemistry is overcome when many difficult concepts are made clearer through appropriate teaching techniques such as computer assisted instruction. More so, abstract concepts which pose difficulties are easily understood when given e-visual explanations. Ekundayo (2022) investigated the effects of CAI on students' achievement in chemistry among boys and girls in public secondary schools. The result from the study showed that there was no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in both the experimental and the control. Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) also investigated on the effect of CAI on senior secondary students' achievement in chemical reaction and equilibrium in Egbeda local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. The instrument used in the study was the chemical reaction and equilibrium achievement test (CREAT). The students' scores from CREAT were collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The results showed a significant difference between the mean achievement of students taught chemical reaction and equilibrium using CAI and those taught using a conventional teaching strategy. Thus, the students taught using CAI performed better than their counterparts. Oluwadara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) conducted a study on the comparative effects of an individualized computer based instruction and the modified conventional strategy on students' academic achievement in organic chemistry, the findings revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught organic chemistry using individualized computer based instructional package and the modified conventional strategy ($f_{1, 65} = 0.228, p=0.635 > 0.05$). Also, no significant difference was found between the academic performance of male and female students who used the individualized CBI ($f_{1, 65} = 0.050, p=0.823 > 0.05$). Titus, Justina and Sylvester (2015) also established that CAI positively affects students' achievement and retention ability.

Reinforcement is strategic skill that could be applied when students are taught chemistry concept to motivate students' interest by way of rewards or praise. This may create motivational stimulus which brings about a change in behaviour. Afirm (2015) identified two types of reinforcement the positive and negative reinforcement. He described the positive reinforcement as the delivery of a reinforcer to increase appropriate behavior while the negative reinforcement is the removal of an aversive event or condition which also increase appropriate behavior. In the educational context grade, praise, medal and other prizes awarded to students are examples of positive reinforcer Rezaul (2013). A study conducted by (Alam, Alay & Alam 2018), proved that positive reinforcement effects students' academic performance with no gender related difference. By comparing

scores of experimental and control group subjects mean for both control and experimental group is 0.5 and calculated value of “t” is 2.50 which is significant on 0.5.

Sex is another important variable that was considered in this study. Sex refers to the state of being a male or female. Every society, ethnic group and culture has specific roles for male which differs from that of the female. This analytic concept describes the sociological roles, cultural responsibilities and expectations of men and women in a given society or cultural setting. The importance of investigating performance with regards to sex is based primitively on the socio-cultural distinction between girls and boys. these discrepancies have extended to some vocations and professions for example agriculture, engineering, arts and crafts work are regarded as men ‘s profession while others such as catering, typing, nursing tailoring, hair dressing etc. are often seen as female profession. Complex and difficult tasks are assigned to boys whereas girls are expected to handle the relatively easy and less demanding tasks. As a result of this way of thinking the larger society has tended to see girls as a weaker sex”. Consequently, an average Nigerian girl goes to school with these fixed stereotypes. This study therefore, seeks to determine the interaction of sex on the two learning approaches (computer assisted and reinforcement) and how it influences learning outcomes.

Learning outcomes can be influenced by school location. The school location refers to the geographical area where the school is sited which is either urban or rural. The rural schools are schools located in the villages where some social amenities like electricity, pipe born water, health care facilities and good roads are lacking, students residing in these areas lack exposure. The urban schools are schools sited in towns and are highly favoured with necessary social the amenities with different cultural diversities as such students’ residing in urban areas are more exposed than students in rural schools. Due to this factor’s location is most likely to influence students learning outcomes. The findings of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas. This study will also compare the learning outcomes of urban and rural students that received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach with the view to determine effects on learning outcome.

Statement of the Research Problem

Students’ failure in chemistry has been a major concern among researchers. The causes of students’ failure have been attributed to a lot of factors which are teachers’ poor qualification, poor method of teaching, lack of teaching experience, and failing to use the instructional materials Ojukwu (2016). However, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2021): in their report, "call to action for science education: building opportunity for the future," the national academies emphasize the necessity of innovative teaching approaches to enhance science education quality. They argue that traditional methods often fail to engage students effectively, leading to suboptimal learning outcomes. Lecture based instruction does not motivate students to learn and there is no one - its – all teaching approach (Tumay, 2016). Flexible teachers must use innovative teaching strategies that adapt information to learners of all background and abilities in a supportive classroom environment (Sibomana et. al., 2021).

Computer assisted is an innovative teaching strategy where students are fully involved in the teaching and learning process. It is an interactive model of instruction that can take the form of power point presentation, pictures and images displayed through the overhead projectors. This enable the students to visually engage and create pictures and imaginations of what is been taught. Students need activities that motivate them to learn. The reinforcement learning approach is another teaching strategy that will cause students to be fully engaged in the learning process. The computer assisted and reinforcement method that has the ability to stimulate and bring students to focus may be a better option than the traditional method. The problem of the study therefore is: what is the effect of computer assisted instruction and reinforcement instructional approach on chemistry students’ learning?

Research questions

1. What is the difference in mean learning outcome scores on chemistry between students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement approach?
2. What is the interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores?
3. What is the difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted - instruction?
4. What is the difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

Hypotheses

Four research hypotheses were raised for this study. They are

- Ho₁. There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.
- Ho₂. There is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores.
- Ho₃. There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted- instruction.
- Ho₄. There is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.

Methodology

The design of the study is pretest posttest planned variation quasi - experimental research design. Two experimental groups were adopted for this research without a control group. The first group received treatment with the use of computer assisted – instruction while the second group received treatment with the reinforcement learning approach and the effects of these two groups on student’s learning outcomes were compared. The quasi – experimental research design was deployed because randomization of subject into group were impossible due to the adoption of intact classes. The study also employed the planned variation because it compared the effects of the two instructional strategies on students’ learning outcomes

The aggregate figure of 18,879 senior secondary year two chemistry students in the 473 government secondary schools in delta state formed the population for this study. Some of the difficult SSII chemistry topics outlined by students in various research findings were selected for this study. This formed the basis for the selection of SSII students that were used for the study. 512 SSII chemistry students drawn from 10 government mixed secondary schools in delta state were used for the study. The stratified sampling technique was used to group the schools into two: urban and rural. Five schools were selected from each group using simple random sampling technique. The stratified sampling was used to ensure that all the schools in the urban and rural were adequately represented. In the computer-assisted instruction group 252 students were selected, which comprised 134 students from urban location and 118 from rural location while 112 were male and 140 were female. In the reinforcement learning instructional approach, 260 students were selected which comprised 140 students from urban location and 120 from rural location while 115 were male and 145 were female. The chemistry assessment test was used to obtain data. It consisted of 50 multiple choice questions drawn from WAEC past question on the following chemistry topics: ionization, and stoichiometry. The treatment lasted for four weeks. The chemistry assessment test was also used to measure students learning outcomes. The learning package for this study was the lesson plan prepared by the researcher for the computer assisted instruction and the reinforcement learning approach to cover for the four-week instruction which was handed over to the chemistry teachers in the sampled schools to prepare them for the various steps to follow in the teaching of the selected chemistry concept. The lesson plan contains the topic to be taught for four weeks, the stated objectives for each period and the necessary steps and procedures that the instructors are to follow to enhance proper understanding of concepts.

The face validity of the chemistry assessment test was determined by experts in the field. They critically examined the test items accordingly to see whether it appeared to test what it aims to test, looking at the logical relationship between questions and the objectives of the study. The content validity of the chemistry assessment test was assured using table of specification ensuring that the content covered all topics spelt out in the four weeks lesson plan.

Presentation of Results

All the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. All the research hypothesis were tested using independent sampled t- test.

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in mean learning outcome scores on chemistry between students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome of the pretest and posttest scores of students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement were compared. this is shown in table 1.

Table 1. mean and standard deviation of pretest and posttest learning outcome scores of chemistry students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach

group	N	pretest	Pretest	posttest	posttest	mean gain
computer- assisted instruction	252	18.28	6.499	62.61	13.025	44.33
reinforcement learning approach	260	18.15	7.699	53.49	13.089	33.34

From the result shown in table 1. The difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students exposed to computer assisted instruction is 44.33 whereas students exposed to reinforcement learning approach had a mean gain of 35.34 which is the mean difference between pretest and posttest scores. This is an indication that there is a variation in the mean learning outcome scores of students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach where students taught with computer assisted outperformed their counterparts taught with reinforcement learning approach.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement learning instructional approach.

The pretest mean learning outcome scores of the students in the two experimental groups were compared using the independent sample t - test to ascertain if there is a significant difference before the treatment and to also ensure that the right statistical tool was employed.

Table 2: summary of independent sample t- test comparison of pretest mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning instructional approach.

Method	N	x	sd	df	t- cal	sig.(2 –tail)	decision
Computer- assisted instruction	252	18.28	6.499	123	0.95	0.925	NS
Reinforcement learning approach	260	18.15	7.699				

$P \geq 0.05$ NS = Not Significant

Table 2. shows that there is no significant difference between the pretest mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach, $t = 0.95$, $p (0.925)$. Thus, the null hypothesis was tested using the independent sample t- test.

Table 3: summary of independent sample t- test comparison of posttest mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach

Method	N	x	sd	df	t- cal	sig.(2 –tail)	decision
Computer- assisted instruction	252	62.61	13.025	115	3.869	0.00	sig
Reinforcement learning approach	260	53.49	13.089				

$p \leq 0.05$

Table 3: shows a significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students taught with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach where $t = 3.869$, $p (0.000) \leq 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis one is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students that received treatment with computer assisted instruction and students taught using reinforcement learning approach

Research Question 2:

What is the interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores

The research questions were answered by comparing the pretest and posttest mean learning outcome scores of students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach this is shown in table 4.

Table 4: the mean and standard deviation on interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on chemistry students' learning outcome.

Test	Sex	Computer -assisted			Reinforcement		
		n	x	sd	n	x	sd
pretest	male	112	20.79	7.951	37	18.86	7.885
	female	140	15.58	2.580	34	17.38	7.467

posttest	total	252	18.28	6.499	71	18.15	7.669
	male	115	62.39	11.796	37	54.89	13.501
	female	145	63.08	14.350	34	51.97	12.648
	total	260	62.61	13.025	71	53.49	13.089

Table 4 shows no interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on students learning outcome this is because at all level of sex there was a higher mean learning outcome scores among male and female students who received treatment with computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach. this can be justified from the posttest mean learning outcome for male and female students exposed to computer assisted which is 62.39 and 63.08 and the posttest mean learning outcome of male and female students exposed to reinforcement is 54.89 and 51.97 respectively.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students mean learning outcome scores.

This hypothesis was test using independent sample t – test the result is shown in table 5:

Table 5: independent sample t – test showing interaction effects between teaching methods and sex on chemistry students learning outcome score

	sex	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
computer-assisted	male	112	62.39	11.796	52	-192	0.849	ns
	female	140	63.08	14.350				
reinforcement	male	115	54.89	13.501	69	0.939	0.351	ns
	female	145	51.97	12.648				

$$p \geq 0.05$$

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of male and female students who were taught chemistry with the computer assisted instruction, $t = -.192$ p (0.849) and there was also no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of male and female students exposed to reinforcement learning approach, $t = 0.939$ p (0.351).this indicates that there is no significant interaction effect between sex and and teaching methods among students taught chemistry using computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach. Based on the finding of this study, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant interaction effect of the teaching methods (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement learning approach) and sex on students' mean learning outcome scores.

Research Question 3:

What is the difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted - instruction?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students exposed to computer assisted were compared as shown in table 6.

Table 6: comparison of posttest scores by location for computer-assisted method

method	location	n	mean	sd	mean difference
computer- assisted	urban	134	64.83	11.683	3.8
	rural	118	61.03	13.870	

Table 6 shows that urban students taught chemistry with the computer assisted method had a mean learning outcome score of 64.83 with standard deviation of 11.683 and their counterparts in rural schools had mean learning outcome score of 61.03 with standard deviation 13.870. The mean difference between the urban and rural students is 3.8 which falls in favour of the urban students. The hypothesis was tested to verify if this difference is significant.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted – instruction.

The hypothesis was tested by comparing the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students who received treatment with computer assisted method using independent sample t – test as shown in table 7.

Table 7: independent sample t – test comparison of mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with computer assisted method

Method	location	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
computer-assisted	urban	134	64.83	11.683	52	1.072	0.289	ns
	rural	118	61.03	13.873				

p ≥ 0.05, ns = not significant

Table 7 shows that there is no significant variation between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with the computer assisted method, $t = 1.072$, $p (0.289) \geq 0.05$ thus, the null hypothesis three is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry using computer assisted instruction.

Research Question 4:

What is the difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach?

To answer this research question, the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students exposed to reinforcement learning approach were compared as shown in table 8.

Table 8: mean and standard deviation of learning outcome scores of urban and rural student taught chemistry using reinforcement learning instructional approach

method	location	n	mean	sd	mean difference
Reinforcement	urban	140	56.27	14.321	4.81
	rural	120	51.46	11.879	

Table 8 shows that urban students taught chemistry with the reinforcement learning approach had a mean learning outcome score of 56.27 with standard deviation of 14.321 and their counterparts in rural schools had mean learning outcome score of 51.46 with standard deviation 11.879. The mean difference between the urban and rural students is 4.81 which falls in favour of the urban students. The hypothesis was tested to verify if this difference is significant.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement instructional approach.

The hypothesis was tested by comparing the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural chemistry students who received treatment with reinforcement learning approach using independent sample t – test as shown in table 9.

Table 9: independent sample t – test comparison of mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with reinforcement learning outcome

Method	location	n	x	sd	df	t-cal	sig.(2 tailed)	decision
reinforcement	urban	140	56.27	14.321	69	1.542	0.128	ns
	rural	120	51.46	11.879				

p > 0.05

Table 9 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught chemistry with reinforcement learning, $t = 1.542$, $p (0.128) \geq 0.05$ thus, the null hypothesis four is not rejected. Therefore,

there is no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry using computer assisted instruction.

Discussion of findings

The study investigated the comparative effects of computer assisted instruction and reinforcement learning approach on chemistry students learning outcome. at end of the analysis the study revealed that there was a significant variation in the mean learning outcome scores of chemistry students exposed to computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach which falls in favour of students taught with computer assisted, they had a higher mean score than their counterparts exposed to reinforcement learning approach. this variation in the mean learning outcome score of the computer assisted group suggests students' active participation in class and learning process here, is more interactive and engaging as more difficult concept are made clearer when computer assisted is employed this may have contributed to the higher performance encountered by students in computer assisted group. students in reinforcement learning approach group may not have performed better than the computer assisted because the reinforcement learning approach is the process of encouraging a belief or pattern of behavior by way of reward to get positive feedback which may either improve students' achievement if the students are motivated by this reward and cause low achievement if students are not motivated by this reward which will equally show low participation in the learning process. This may have accounted for the low mean learning outcome scores of students in reinforcement group. Thus, computer assisted is more effective in enhancing chemistry students learning outcome scores than the reinforcement learning approach. This study is in accordance with the findings of Busari, Ernest and Ugwuanyi (2016) who reported a significant difference between the mean achievement of students taught chemical reaction and equilibrium using cai and those taught using a conventional teaching strategy in favour of the computer assisted. the finding of the study is also in compliance with the findings of Titus, Justina and Sylvester (2015) who established that computer assisted positively affects students' achievement and retention ability in the subject. This study is not in agreement with the findings of Oluwadarara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) who found no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught organic chemistry using individualized computer based instructional package and the modified conventional strategy. consequently, researchers have made comparison between computer assisted instruction and other teaching methods to ascertain the most effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes however, literature has not reported any comparison between computer assisted and reinforcement learning approach to ascertain the most effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes.

The study further established that there is no significant interaction effect of the teaching method (computer assisted instruction and reinforcement) and sex on students' mean learning outcome scores. This simply implies that sex is not a determinant of the learning outcome scores of chemistry students taught with the use of computer assisted and the reinforcement learning approach. The reason why there was no interaction effect of the two-teaching method on sex could be due to the mode of instruction employed by the teacher. Equal learning will take place when the right procedure is adopted to cater for students observed behaviours and assumption during teaching and learning process. therefore, sex have no influence on chemistry students' learning outcome when taught using computer assisted and sex does not equally influence chemistry students learning outcome when taught using reinforcement learning approach. The result of this finding is compliance with the findings of Oluwadarara, Adetunmbi, Lukuman and Mohammed (2017) who reported no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students who used the individualized computer based instruction. the study is also in agreement with the findings of Ekundayo (2022) who found no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in both the experimental and control group. The study also agrees with the findings of Alam, Alay & Alam 2018 who proved that positive reinforcement effects students' academic performance with no gender related difference.

The study further revealed that there was no significant difference between the chemistry mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using computer assisted – instruction. This is implying that teaching with computer assisted has no influence in the learning outcome of chemistry students in urban and rural location. Therefore, location will not determine the learning outcome scores of students taught chemistry with computer assisted instruction. This justifies the interactive nature of computer assisted as it helps to blend learning by equipping students with the skills to think and find solution to critical concepts in chemistry. The result of this finding is not in line with the result of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) who revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas.

the study again, establish that there is no significant difference between the mean learning outcome scores of urban and rural students taught using reinforcement approach. This implies that the use of reinforcement learning approach in the teaching of the selected chemistry concept does not influence the learning outcome scores of chemistry students in the urban and rural areas. This is an indication that the use of reinforcement learning approach will not cause any change or determine

the learning outcome scores of chemistry students in urban and rural location. The finding of this study is contrary to the finding of Awodun and Oyeniyi (2018) who revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in urban and rural school located areas.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this present study, it is therefore concluded that computer assisted is the most appropriate in the teaching of difficult concept in chemistry, it empowers students' learning and influence their learning outcome more exceedingly than the reinforcement learning approach.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Adoption of computer-assisted instruction (CAI):** Teachers, particularly chemistry educators, should integrate computer-assisted instruction into their teaching practices. Its interactive and engaging nature makes it a powerful tool for enhancing students' understanding of difficult concepts and improving learning outcomes.
2. **Training and support for Teachers:** Educational institutions should provide training and professional development opportunities for teachers to effectively utilize computer-assisted instruction. This will ensure that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to implement CAI in their classrooms.
3. **Incorporating CAI into curriculum design:** Curriculum planners and policymakers should consider incorporating computer-assisted instruction as a standard teaching method in secondary school science curricula, particularly for challenging subjects like chemistry.

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